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Citizen Empowerment Handbook

Executive Summary

The FOODITY Citizen Empowerment Handbook Process provides a comprehensive guide to participatory research methodologies across four key chapters, offering practical insights and replicable approaches for researchers and practitioners.

PhotoVoice Methodology (Chapter 2). Presents a detailed overview of the PhotoVoice method, including its structural framework, guiding questions, and implementation considerations. It offers a step-by-step workshop guide and documents PhotoVoice processes conducted in three different countries, providing both theoretical guidance and practical application.

Citizen Dialogues (Chapter 3). Explores the concept of citizen dialogues within the FOODITY project context. It provides a structured approach to organizing dialogues, showcasing best-practice examples and diverse dialogue formats. The chapter includes detailed accounts of citizen dialogues implemented in Sofia, Coimbra, and Vienna, along with a comprehensive summary of

experiences and results.

Awareness-Raising Campaign (Chapter 4). Details the development of an awareness-raising campaign, covering methodological approaches, campaign content, and key messaging. It focuses on identifying target personas, tailoring communication strategies, and implementing campaigns across various channels. The section critically reflects on campaign experiences, highlighting successes, challenges, and key learnings.

Conclusions and Recommendations (Chapter 5). The final chapter synthesizes insights from the project's participatory activities across three countries. It provides strategic recommendations for future initiatives, drawing from the project's comprehensive research and engagement processes.

The handbook serves as a valuable resource for researchers, policymakers, and practitioners interested in participatory research methodologies, offering a structured, transferable approach to community engagement and knowledge co-creation.

The FOODITY project

The main goal of FOODITY is to create a European ecosystem of digital solutions that contributes to a more sustainable and healthy food and nutrition system — respecting citizens' rights to personal data sovereignty.

FOODITY will run a **2M€ pilot development programme for creating 12 data-driven solutions** to demonstrate the potential of data-driven innovation in food and nutrition while guaranteeing the user's full control and ownership over their personal data.

These innovations will provide novel solutions to existing research and technical challenges to achieve the four Food 2030 (the EU's research and innovation policy to build better food systems by 2030) key priorities: (1) Nutrition for sustainable and healthy diets, (2) Food systems supporting a healthy planet, (3) Circularity and resource efficiency, and (4) Innovation and empowering communities.

Participants in the pilot development programme will be selected through two open calls to be launched in July and October 2023, respectively. Eligible beneficiaries will be research and technology organisations (RTOs) and universities, small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), social innovation actors and training organisations.

The programme will provide its beneficiaries with a set of value-added services: from one-to-one mentoring to training on technical, business, and legal matters, as well as technical and financial support (up to 187.500€ per beneficiary) for developing their pilots.

From January 2023 and until December 2025, the FOODITY consortium, comprised of 7 partners, will join forces to make this a reality.

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Introduction

This handbook is organised into several sections that provide both practical guidance and insights into specific experiences, results, and recommendations from the FOODITY project.

Chapter 2 addresses the PhotoVoice method. Section 2.2.1 offers an introduction to the structure of PhotoVoice. Section 2.2.2 addresses the specific question used within the FOODITY project to guide the PhotoVoice process. Section 2.2.3 presents additional considerations for initiating a PhotoVoice process. Section 2.3 provides a step-by-step guide for conducting a three-part PhotoVoice workshop. This guide can be directly applied to facilitate a group PhotoVoice process. Finally, Section 2.4 details the three PhotoVoice processes carried out as part of the FOODITY project in three different countries.

Chapter 3 focuses on citizen dialogues. Section 3.1 begins by explaining the concept of citizen dialogue, and Section 3.1.3 specifies what these

dialogues entail within the context of the FOODITY project. Section 3.2 outlines the organisation of a citizen dialogue and key aspects to consider (detailed in Section 3.2.1). In Section 3.3, a series of best-practice examples are presented, covering various formats to illustrate the diverse ways these dialogues can be structured. Chapter 3.4 describes the three specific citizen dialogues conducted for the FOODITY project in Sofia (3.4.1), Coimbra (3.4.2), and Vienna (3.4.3). Finally, Chapter 3.5 summarises experiences and results from these dialogues.

Chapter 4 covers the awareness-raising campaign. Section 4.1 introduces the methodological approach used to develop the campaign. Section 4.2 details the campaign content and key messages. Section 4.3 focuses on personas and target groups, outlining who the campaign aimed to reach and how messages were tailored to these groups. Section 4.4 describes the final campaigns and activities implemented, including

information on content, duration, channels, and audience reactions. Lastly, Section 4.5 reflects on the experiences from the campaign, highlighting what worked well, the challenges encountered, and lessons learned.

Finally, Chapter 5 presents conclusions drawn from the participatory activities conducted as part of the FOODITY project across three countries. It also offers recommendations to guide similar future initiatives, based on the insights and lessons learned from these activities.

PhotoVoice Methodology

2.1 Introduction

In FOODITY, the PhotoVoice method is used to find out about citizens' perception of data privacy and data sovereignty of food and nutrition data, and to empower citizens in data sharing and keeping control about their personal nutrition and health data. In this in-depth engagement process, the state-of-the-art knowledge in the field based on a literature review is complemented. Thus, this technique helps the FOODITY team to:

- Support a bottom-up empowerment process in three hubs.
- Raising awareness on the topic and reaching out to a larger group, by giving individuals a voice and preparing exhibitions with results.
- Get qualitative insights on the perception and understanding of data sovereignty and privacy by citizens in three hubs (Coimbra, Vienna and Sofia).

This guideline helps the teams in the hubs to conduct their own PhotoVoice process. They get a general introduction to the method, precise instructions on how to implement the process, as well as practical tools such as check-lists and other necessary materials.

A detailed guide leads through the sessions of this three-day workshop series and is designed to be implemented step-by-step. Finally, the exact adherence to the process allows for a comparison between the three hubs.

2.1.1 PhotoVoice - an overview

PhotoVoice projects aim at empowerment. Coming from photojournalism, PhotoVoice projects empower people to inform others and participate in decisions on their own lives or the communities' development (PhotoVoice facilitators guide, page 5). The PhotoVoice methodology was created by Caroline Wang in 1992 (Reece 2021). A PhotoVoice workshop is a tool to give people a voice, to engage people who often do not have the opportunity share their views or to influence decisions (Reece 2021). Thus, it is an empowerment tool, as all participants can tell their stories from their perspective and in their way. Social sciences and social anthropology use participatory photo and video making as a research tool, to help and stimulate people to explain their thoughts, concerns, wishes etc.

PhotoVoice participants are “asked to represent their personal point of view or opinion by photographing scenes relevant” to them or their community. Thus, it is very important to provide a carefully defined research question to start the PhotoVoice process.

The specificity of a PhotoVoice method is the active role of the participants, respondents determine which subjects are in the photographs and explain them; they introduce subjects that are important for them in relation to a question. The photograph is part of a communication and interpretation process that is continued in the group process. In the examination of the photograph, a new reality emerges in the confrontation with the material and new readings are possible. New details can become visible for both the photographer and the researcher (Kolb 2008).

2.2 Preparation

The PhotoVoice process needs good preparation to run smoothly. Therefore, it is described here i) the PhotoVoice structure, where design is based on, ii) aims and objectives and research questions and iii) a checklist, what to consider.

2.2.1 PhotoVoice structure

The PhotoVoice method follows a seven-block structure (Jongeling u. a. 2016; Layh u. a. 2020; Blackman 2007)^{1,2,3}, where each block has a specific goal:

Blocks addressing photography:

- **Block 1 – PhotoVoice training – getting started**

- **Block 2 – The basics of photography**

- **Block 3 – How to work a camera?**

These blocks are dedicated to understanding the basics of photography. Based on the pre-knowledge of participants, sufficient time for blocks 1 to 3 must be planned. E.g., it makes a difference if all participants use smart phones in their daily life or if you work with a group, who do not have any kind

of camera. In the FOODITY project, it is expected to work with experienced people, and thus, enter these blocks by stimulating photo discussion and reflecting the touch and power of pictures.

- **Block 4 – The research question**

In this block, the process is linked to the topic and the specific research question. Participants get input about the topic and important contexts. Moreover, in this block the research question is presented and reflected with participants. A clear and common understanding of the research question is crucial.

- **Block 5 – Fieldwork**

Participants answer the research question by taking pictures. They start the individual selection process. This takes place between workshop day 1 and 2 individually by each participant.

- **Block 6 – Selection process**

In this block, a categorisation of pictures takes place. The group selects the most important aspects and themes.

- **Block 7 – Exhibition**

On the last workshop day ideas for the exhibition for stakeholders or the broader community are prepared. The results are used to raise awareness on the topic.

¹ Jongeling u. a. 2016: Jongeling, Silvia, Marko Bakker, Ruth van Zorge, und Karijn van Kakebeeke. 2016. "PhotoVoice-Facilitators-guide". <https://rutgers.international/wp-content/uploads/2021/09/Photovoice-Facilitators-guide.pdf>

² Layh u. a. 2020: Layh, Sandra, Anja Feldhorst, Rebecca Althaus, Monika Bradna, und Petra Wihofszky. 2020. "PhotoVoice-Forschung mit Jugendlichen – ein Leitfaden zur Durchführung". In *Partizipative Forschung*, herausgegeben von Susanne Hartung, Petra Wihofszky, und Michael T. Wright, 233–62. Wiesbaden: Springer Fachmedien Wiesbaden. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-658-30361-7_8

³ Blackman, Anna. 2007. *The PhotoVoice Manual: A Guide to Designing and Running Participatory Photography Projects*. First edition. London: PhotoVoice.

Figure 1 PhotoVoice structure overview

2.2.2 FOODITY aim, objective and research question

Aims and objectives give a workshop purpose and direction - so they do for the PhotoVoice workshop. The FOODITY aims and objectives provide the framework. An **aim** can be defined as “an intention or aspiration; what you hope to achieve at the end of the project” (Jongeling u. a. 2016 p. 12).

The aim is to empower citizens to express their concerns and their requirements in relation to handling of food and nutrition data. Related to this, we aim at getting in depth insights in citizens’ concerns and requirements regarding data privacy and data sovereignty.

An **objective** is defined as “ a goal or steps on the way to meeting the aim - how you will achieve your aims” (Jongeling u. a. 2016 p. 12). The FOODITY PhotoVoice workshop has the following objectives:

- Gather citizens’ opinion on data privacy and data sovereignty regarding food and nutrition data.
- Identification of important fields of interest regarding the handling of food and nutrition data.
- Learn about concerns and wishes regarding the use of personal food and nutrition data.
- Creation of an exhibition to raise awareness.

A specific and clear research question is key for a successful workshop. According to Jongeling et al. (2016 p. 13) in a PhotoVoice process the research question “aims to find something out about the individual. [...] So the research question is always defined in a reflective way and asks for the participants’ meaning, experience, change, view or opinion”.

Characteristics of the PhotoVoice research questions are i) personal, ii) open, iii) clear and specific, iv) directly related to the lives of participants, and v) answers can be shown through pictures.

To reach FOODITY’s aims and objectives the following research questions were identified:

- What is important for you when dealing with your nutrition data?
- What should not happen with your data?
- Which kind of service would you be interested in?

2.2.3 What to consider

A PhotoVoice workshop is an in-depth engagement process, where no claim is made to representativeness. In the FOODITY project it is aimed at engaging 15 persons maximum. The organisers aim at a random mix of participants in terms of age, gender, background, education level, etc. to be able to integrate different perspectives.

A successful PhotoVoice workshop needs good preparation. There are many aspects to consider regarding the participants, the location and the equipment. Additionally, PhotoVoice organisers must prepare a suitable consent form for participants.

Checklists for FOODITY PhotoVoice workshops:

The participants

- Participants should reflect your target group
- Strive for a diverse group composition (age, background, gender, etc.)
- All participants do have a smartphone and are familiar in using it for photographing
- Consider to have one facilitator for every six participants

The location(s)

- The workshop venue must provide sufficient space
- Consider break out options
- Room with daylight
- Facilities for charging smartphones or cameras
- Central and easy to reach for participants

Equipment and materials

- Consent forms
- Invitation letter
- Participant list
- Laptop and projector
- Flip chart, stand and markers
- Pin wall(s) and pins
- Moderation cards in different colours
- Post-its in different colours and sizes
- charger for different smartphones
- Printer (colour)
- A4 (or A5) printing paper and/or photo paper
- Scissors, hangers, glue, and other materials for creative work
- Handouts of presentations
- Handouts for procedure
- PowerPoint XML (pptx) presentation
- Certificate for participation

2.3 Step-by-step guideline for FOODITY PhotoVoice process

In this chapter, it is provided the step-by-step guideline of the FOODITY PhotoVoice process by providing details for each session per workshop day and the tasks that need to be done between the workshop days. The design of this process builds on the before described PhotoVoice structure. Each session is dedicated to one of the seven blocks.

The weight per block and the time allocated is adapted to the FOODITY target group, who is expected to be familiar with photographing and is used to using smartphones and other digital tools.

2.3.1 Day 1: Block 1 to block 4

Session 1 – Welcome and introduction

On this first day, people might meet each other for the first time and most of them – probably all – might not have participated in a PhotoVoice workshop yet.

Thus, a format has been designed that allows for exchange and team building and that clarifies processes, uncertainties and the research question before participants start their field work.

Objectives

- All participants know and understand the goals and non-goals of the workshop/process
- Introduction of Agenda
- Workshop etiquette is agreed among the group

Time

10 min

Materials

It is suggested to avoid pptx presentations at this point of the workshop and thus suggest to prepare creatively designed flip charts for displaying the

- agenda,
- goals & non-goals, and
- workshop etiquette

Instructions

1. Prepare an open and warm welcome.
2. Make sure that Agenda, goal and non-goals are well visible attached in the room.
3. Introduce workshop etiquette and agree with the group on rules.

Session 2 – Warm up

Objectives

- Participants get to know each other
- Create open and relaxed atmosphere
- Enter the topic

Time

05 min: Name game

20 min: Sociometric constellation

Materials

- Large room (NO tables; put chairs on side, if necessary)
- Optional: Floor markers for the sociometric constellation

Instructions

Name game

1. Participants stand in a circle.
2. One person starts to name the person's name on either his/her/their right or left side. This person continues. And so on.
3. Take the time, how long the group takes for one circle.

4. Try another faster round.
5. This can be done 3 or more rounds (depending on group size and speed).

Sociometric constellation:

1. All participants are standing in the room.
2. The facilitator asks different questions, and participants position themselves according to their answer.
3. The facilitator asks some participants to explain why they have chosen this answer, or why they have positioned themselves at this stage, and ask them for more details. All questions are low threshold at this stage of the workshop.

The following questions for the FOODITY PhotoVoice workshop are identified:

- Where are you living?
- Imaging in this room is the map of the country/home town/Europe. People position themselves geographically.
 - A sub question for some individuals could target their background.
- Who of you is using a smartphone?
 - Yes: on the right side of the room.

- No: on the left side of the room.
- Private data – what is it?
 - Provide a scale from “I know exactly what is meant by that” to “I have no idea what exactly is understood under private data”.
 - Choose some, and let them explain what they think private data comprises.
 - Complement and explain what is understood by private data, if needed.
- Who of you never shared data so far?
 - Yes: right side of the room
 - No: left side of the room
 - Ask why, when, where, etc.

Session 3 – Introduction of process / consent / rules / collaboration contract

Objectives

- All participants understand the process of the PhotoVoice workshop
- All participants give their informed consent
- Collaboration contracts are agreed

Time

15 min

Materials

- Presentation of the PhotoVoice process
- Informed consent form
- Projector/screen

Instructions

1. Inform participants about the PhotoVoice process, and how the process is organised. What is going to happen in the workshops, what happens in between, etc.
2. Inform participants about practicalities (e.g. breaks, chargers for phones/cameras, meeting points, etc.)

3. Inform participants about what kind of pictures can be taken (What is allowed, what isn't)
4. Introduce consent form and let participants sign
5. Clarify, if all agree to share their photos for the exhibition and the citizen dialogue

Session 4 – Feel and touch of picture

Objectives

- Participants get a feeling how photos tell stories
- Participants exchange how photos stimulate associations

Time

30 min

Materials

- Photo cards (around 80 pieces)

Instructions

1. Raise a **question** you want to discuss, eg: Your next goal? Or, your most exciting experience? etc.

2. Put all photo cards on a table (or on the floor).
3. Ask all participants to choose one/two pictures best explaining/showing their answer.
4. Participants choose one/two pictures explaining their answer.
5. Participants remember the chosen picture but leave it on the table - thus, more than one person can choose the same picture.
6. Present one after the next: Participants tell the group why they have selected the specific picture.
7. Reflect about the process (what was surprising? How was your experience in general?).
8. Attach pics to pin wall, adding post-its with names of participants and their answers (mini exhibition).

Session 5 – Introduction to the topic

Objectives

- Participants are introduced to the topic
- Participants are informed about state of the art

Time

40 min

Materials

- Moderation cards
- Flip chart markers
- Pin wall, pins

Instructions

Step 1 15 min

1. PowerPoint **presentation**, showing basic facts and background knowledge regarding the topic. Allow for questions and answers for clarification.

Step 2 25 min

Interactive mind map

Ask your participants to reflect:

- What strikes you?
- What are your thoughts about that?
- What questions come up?

2. Start with the topic attached in the middle of the pin wall (“My food and nutrition data”);
3. Participants individually write their thoughts, concerns, expectations, etc. on moderation cards (only one aspect per card!)
4. In plenary collaboratively set up the mind map on a pin wall adding participants’ thoughts, concerns, expectations, etc. related to each other.

Session 6 – Research question

Objectives

- Participants get to know the research question
- Clarification and understanding

Time

10 min

Materials

- Flip chart with research questions

Instructions

1. Uncover prepared flip chart outlining the research question.
2. Read the research question aloud.
3. Allow questions, clarify doubts, etc. until participants feel confident that they have understood the question and can answer it.

Session 7 – Instruction for FOODITY PhotoVoice process

Objectives

- Participants become clear about the procedure and the next steps

Time

20 min

Materials

- Handout for participants

Instructions

1. Present and discuss according to the outline:
 - Deadline for sending the photos (max. 3)
 - E-mail address for sending in
 - Research question
 - What kind of pictures (persons, abstract, selfie, etc. allowed)
 - Clarify ethical issues
2. Clarify any open questions regarding the procedure.

Session 8 – Closing round

Objectives

- Smooth closure of day 1

Time

10 min

Instructions

Participants sit in a circle, get the opportunity, one after the other, to say how they feel, what bothers them, what they liked, etc. (Limit the time to approx. half a minute per person).

2.3.2 Between day 1 and day 2: block 5

Block 5

Field work - participants follow the procedure handout, take photos and send them to the research team. The research team prepares **two prints** of each photo for workshop day 2. These prints do not necessarily have to be on photo paper already. At this stage adequate size for working on them is more important.

2.3.3 Day 2: Block 6

Session 9 – Check-In

Objectives

- Participants arrive at the workshop
- Recap and practising names of participants

Time

10 min

Materials

- Little (soft) ball

Instructions

1. Stand in a circle and throw the ball to a person by calling his/her name.
2. This person looks for another person and continues.
3. Make sure that all participants get a turn, preferably several times.

Session 10 – Reflection round

Objectives

- Reflection and sharing of experiences

Time

25 min

Materials

- Talking object (Stick, ball, stone etc)

Instructions

Sit in a circle (without tables) and ask participants about their experience of photo taking. What was easy, difficult, surprising? What do they want to share with the group? Use a “talking object” to be handed over from one person to the other. Only the person with the object is allowed to speak. All others just listen.

Session 11 – Dialogic Analysis

Objectives

- Discuss and code photos
- Identify clusters / image sets

Time

65 min

Materials

- Printed photos of all participants
- Audio recording device

Instructions

1. Split into (three) smaller groups.
2. Audio-record each group session.
3. One person after the next presents his/her chosen pictures and explains their meanings.
4. Guiding questions for facilitators:
 - What can we see in this picture?
 - Why did you take this frame?
 - What does it represent/ mean to you?
 - How does it answer the research question?
5. Other group members can raise questions or tell what they think is noteworthy.

Before handing over to the next person, each photo gets a “code” on the back side. This code should best describe or summarise what is **meant** with the photo by the photographer (not visual similarities). The codes help the group to cluster their photos and make their **image sets**.

Session 12 – Plenary - Bringing all group results together

Objectives

- Finding common **themes**
- Merging group results

Time

30 min

Materials

- Clustered and coded photos of break out groups
- Moderation cards for identified titles of clusters/image sets
- Note taking material
- Audio recording device

Instructions

1. Audio record session
 2. Each group presents their identified image sets.
 3. Other groups complement.
 4. Discuss similarities, differences. Re-define clusters, add new ones.
- Add titles of clusters (**=themes**) on moderation

cards.

5. Hand each participant 5 sticky dots and allow them to put them on their theme(s) they find most relevant.
6. Before closing, give the participants the opportunity to express their level of satisfaction with the group result.

Session 13 – Feedback and Closing

Objectives

- Smooth closure of day 2

Time

15 min

Materials

- note taking material

Instructions

Sit in a circle and have each person in any order (pop-up style) express in just **three words** (not more - be strict) how they feel at the end of this analysis process.

2.3.4 Between day 2 and day 3: Visual Pattern Analysis and external perspective

Objectives

- Complement and prepare results to be fed back to participants on day 3
- Content analysis
- Theorising

Time

1 - 3 days

Materials

- Group result of day 2
- Audio recordings

Instructions

The instructions for this part of the analysis is based on the concept of Grounded Visual Pattern Analysis (Shortt und Warren 2020)⁴. For better understanding it is advisable to read the [background paper](#).

For this analysis work it is recommended to work with a team of 2-3 people to be able to bring in different perspectives. Put the group result in front of you as they were grouped in the workshop (= themes) and look at them carefully.

Step 1 symbolism (the objects, subjects, places, events depicted)

In this first step we look at **WHAT** exactly is depicted in the pictures. Describe what one can see in the photos, and also what NOT. For example, perhaps, it is noteworthy that there are no persons shown, or no daylight etc. Try not to judge or interpret here, but only to describe what is depicted. This can also be small details. Discuss with the team and write post-its with the different descriptions and add them to the photos or make notes in the margin. See an example in Figure 2.

Figure 2 Example of analysis step 1 and step 2

⁴ Shortt, Harriet, und Samantha Warren. 2020. "Photography: Using Instagram in Participant-Led Field Studies". In *Using Arts-Based Research Methods: Creative Approaches for Researching Business, Organisation and Humanities*, herausgegeben von Jenna Ward und Harriet Shortt, 237–70. Palgrave Studies in Business, Arts and Humanities. Cham: Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-33069-9_9

PhotoVoice Methodology

Step 2 composition (camera angle, lighting, aesthetic effects, point-of-view and so on.)

In the next step we take a look at the composition of the photo. **HOW** exactly is something shown and represented? Which camera angle is chosen? Is it looking up, or looking down? Which perspective is taken? Is it frontstage or backstage? Does this picture seem to be deliberately composed or is it just a snapshot? What is the position of the photographer? Is he/she/they also in the photo? Is the photographer inside or outside of the space shown etc.

Again, discuss with the team and write post-its with the different descriptions and add them to the photos or make notes in the margin.

In the next step, write a summary of what you have found in step 1 and 2 in two columns.

Step 3 Theorising. Bringing together the analytical reflection

In the last step, we interpret with all our senses, based on the photos, the discussions, the observed patterns, etc.” taking all multi-sensory, emplaced, spatial aesthetics as clues”. This step is a process of sense-making. Trust your impressions and think analytically about how and why your observations are significant.

Again, discuss with the team and write post-its with the different descriptions and add them to the photos or make notes in the margin.

-
1. Add a third column to the viewing record (as in the Figure 2).
 2. Write your analytical reflections on what the observed patterns might mean in terms of answering our research questions – but also beyond these. Here are guiding questions:
 - How do they compare?
 - How do they contrast?
 - What do the patterns help us more than the dialogues have already shown us?
 - Different interpretations of research questions?
 - etc.
 3. Theorising: Write results (theory) per theme on flip chart.

Theme: visibility		
Stage 1: Symbolic viewing	Stage 2: Compositional viewing	Stage 3: Theorising reflections for theory building
People sitting	No highly staged photos, everyday settings	Considering the theme of visibility, we can see traces of the voyeur / flaneur here
People sitting in groups	Instagram photos (n=6) are more composed and considered though	The distant / long-shot aesthetic connects to issues of panopticon, power, 'overviews', 'helicopter views' of high
Casual-looking meetings	All long shots (no close ups)	
Almost all are communal spaces		
Walkways		

Figure 3 Step 3 – example of table for theorising - reflections for theory building (Shortt und Warren 2020 chapter 9, p. 20)

2.3.5 Day 2: Block 7

Session 14 – Check-in Round

Objectives

- Participants arrive at workshop and see how participants feel
- Collect additional aspects

Time

20 min

Material

- Moderation cards
- Pin-wall
- Pins

Instructions

Facilitator asks: What came to your mind? Are there additional aspects that popped up?
Note taker writes aspects on cards and puts them on the pin-wall.

Session 15 – Presentation and Validation

Objectives

- Common agreement on results

Time

25 min

Material

- Presentation of theory flip charts per theme

Instructions

1. Researcher team presents analysis of aspects and theories; their external perspective.
2. Clarify if everything was understood correctly or if there are things that need to be adapted or corrected.
3. Integrate further aspects (including those collected at the check-in round).

Session 16 – Agreement on design of presentation of results

Objectives

- Common agreement on design/structure/format of final presentation (exhibition)

Time

20 min

Instructions

1. Discuss how the participants want their results presented. If there are different approaches, such as a press release or poster, etc.
2. Explain that smaller groups can work on different formats in the following working session.
3. Consider which aspects (and photos) need to be emphasised. For example, are there some that must be clustered? or is there a specific sequence they want to follow? etc.
4. When everything is clear, start the interactive working session.

Session 17 – Creative preparation of exhibition

Objectives

- Collaborative arrangement of results

Time

60 min

Material

- Any creative material, pens, glue, moderation cards, post-it, scissors, tape, notebooks, miro, ppt, flip chart pens, etc.

Instructions

1. Consider dividing participants in small groups according to e.g. themes, or different exhibition formats of interests.
2. Groups work on the formats they have decided for their exhibition.
3. Support participants in writing titles and captions for their photos that are part of the exhibition.
4. Let participants be creative (e.g. maybe they want to make a collage, or a photostory, or gallery style - everything is allowed).

Session 18 – Group presentations in plenary

Objectives

- Viewing and acknowledging the results

Time

10 min

Instructions

1. All formats are presented (e.g. make a short walk through of all group results)
2. Make photos of the final results and share with participants.
3. Inform that these will also be fed to the projects social media channels.

Session 19 – Closing round

Objectives

- Feedback, closing

Time

15 min

Material

- Certificates

Instructions

1. Closing round: Give sufficient time for each participant (max 1 min per participant) for feedback to the group and the research team. Ask, if the experience has changed anything and what.
2. Facilitator makes notes.
3. Don't forget to take a **group photo** (last chance!)

Farewell

Preferably invite your participants for a drink or whatever you think is suitable.

2.4 FOODITY PhotoVoice workshops

The three FOODITY PhotoVoice workshops demonstrated that the method works very well even for this abstract topic. The teams chose to work with small but highly diverse groups, which enriched the results significantly. In the following sections, the group compositions in the three workshops are described. A visual summary of all results and picture takes can be found in the [FOODITY photo book](#).

2.4.1 Sofia:

The workshop in Sofia took place on 13 June 2023, 20 June 2023, and 5 July 2023 in Schroedinger Bar.

The group consisted of a relatively diverse range of participants, with ages spanning from the mid-20s to late 50s. The initial registration list indicated a near-even gender split, with a female-to-male ratio of 4 to 5. However, due to illness, one female participant had to cancel, and another could only

attend the first event due to unforeseen circumstances, resulting in a final group composition of two women and five men.

The participants came from various professional backgrounds, including chefs, academics, lawyers, and IT developers. Additionally, there was a balanced mix of native Bulgarians and foreign expats from Belgium and England, contributing to the cultural diversity of the group.

2.4.2 Coimbra:

The workshop took place on 23 September 2023 in Coimbra, Portugal.

The group that participated in the Portugal PhotoVoice workshop consisted of seven people.

The group consisted of five women and two men (not including the facilitator and assistant). Their ages ranged from 24 (woman) to 58 (woman). The average age of the participants was 37.6.

All participants had at least a Master's Degree, the majority with a PhD or concluding a PhD. Participants' educational backgrounds included anthropology, engineering, economics, and psychology. Several of the participants were known to each other. Several of the participants have experience with EU-funded projects. None of the participants had previously participated in any activity using the PhotoVoice methodology.

2.4.3 Vienna:

The workshop in Vienna took place on 30 June 2023, 02 July 2023, and 05 July 2023 at ZSI premises in Vienna

The group consisted of 8 diverse participants, with an equal number of females and males. The participants came from various professional backgrounds and ranged in age from 21 to 60. The group included both local residents and individuals with a migration background, adding to the diversity of the event.

Citizen Dialogues

3.1 What is a citizen dialogue?

A dialogue can be characterised as a collaborative process wherein individuals jointly create meaning and shared understanding through conversation. Thus, dialogue methodology involves structured conversations aimed at facilitating the expression of views by all participants while fostering respectful listening and moving towards mutual understanding.

Dialogue serves as a tool for integration, enabling the synthesis of diverse insights into a cohesive whole. A citizen dialogue, on the other hand, represents a specific initiative by policymakers, planners, researchers, or others to engage in conversations with particular communities, affected groups, stakeholders, or residents of specific areas. While there is no singular definition or format for citizen dialogue, two-way communication is a fundamental aspect that encourages genuine conversation among all participants.

Consequently, various formats are employed, whether in-person or online. Some illustrative examples include web dialogues, appreciative inquiry, community dialogues, town hall debates, science cafés.

Further elaboration on these examples will be provided in the subsequent sections.

3.1.1 Citizen Dialogue in FOODITY

The FOODITY project delves into a multifaceted topic, presenting specific challenges in organising citizen dialogue activities. Within this broad subject, various subtopics intersect with societal discourses. Discussions around data privacy, sovereignty, and protection, as well as legal regulations aimed at aligning with European standards for data security and sovereignty, have been ongoing since the inception of General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). On another front lies the expansive domain of nutrition, food, and health, which garners significant interest from a wide spectrum of citizens. Combining these two realms poses a unique challenge for FOODITY: orchestrating dialogue events that are both engaging and informative to pique citizens' curiosity.

To achieve this, the FOODITY team plans to foster interactions between local stakeholders and citizens, providing a platform for questions and conversations. Additionally, collaborating with at least one FOODITY pilot activity is crucial. These pilot initiatives serve as concrete examples, offering starting points for discussions on how to navigate the complexities of food and nutrition data. Furthermore, it is important to incorporate the outcomes of the PhotoVoice workshops into the citizen dialogue event. Like the pilot activities, these outcomes offer valuable discussion points for engaging with local stakeholders and can assist citizens in articulating their inquiries effectively.

In brief, here is the list of components to consider for the FOODITY citizen dialogues:

- Combine the umbrella topic of data with the field of nutrition and food.
- Invite local stakeholders and enable discussion with citizens.
- Engage approximately 70 persons.
- Take up at least one FOODITY pilot example.
- Use PhotoVoice results to structure discussion.
- Consider combining it with a small exhibition of PhotoVoice results.

3.2 Preparing your citizen dialogue

- **Establish a team** dedicated to organising and executing your citizen dialogue.
- **Define clear objectives for the dialogue format.** Determine what you aim to achieve and identify your target audience. Clearly articulate the groups you wish to gather to exchange ideas and perspectives. Consider reaching out to existing groups or communities to streamline recruitment efforts.
- **Identify relevant stakeholders to invite.** These stakeholders should be influential figures capable of capturing the interest of your target audience. Ensure that stakeholders have compelling reasons to participate in the dialogue.
- **Customise an approach tailored to your objectives and target demographics.** Consider the most effective channels to reach your audience and facilitate dialogue. Decide whether you envision a structured panel discussion with stakeholders moderated by a professional facilitator, or if you prefer a more informal format to engage with passersby at a booth.
- **Consider engaging professional facilitators.** Effective facilitation is essential for successful dialogues. Experienced facilitators possess the skills to stimulate discussion, maintain neutrality, and excel at active listening.
- **Develop a discussion guide to steer conversations.** This structured guide should incorporate insights from PhotoVoice workshops and focus discussions on solutions proposed by pilot teams. Additionally, the guide aids in stimulating dialogue and planning the event's timeline.
- **Secure a suitable venue, date, and time for the event.** Choose a location conducive to your chosen format; an inviting atmosphere is crucial for a successful dialogue event. Additionally, consider the optimal date and time frame for your target audience.
- **Initiate an advertising campaign** to generate interest in the dialogue event among your target audience. Determine which communication channels your audience frequents and what specific topics are most likely to pique their interest.

3.2.1 What to consider

- **Warm and welcoming location:**
Choose a location that is inviting and comfortable for participants, with a low threshold for entry and easy accessibility.
- **Information and content provision:**
Provide information and content in a format and language that is appropriate and accessible to your target audience.
- **Date and duration of event:**
Be flexible with the date and duration of the event to accommodate the needs of your target group. Start preparation early, as things often take longer than expected, **including sending out invitations in multiple waves.**
- **Successful invitation processes:**
Use appropriate means, language, and channels to reach your target audience. Consider utilising various media and channels and consult with intermediary institutions to effectively reach their audiences or members.
- **Moderation:**
Ensure that moderation is well-prepared and effective in facilitating constructive dialogue. Work with qualified and skilled facilitators.
- **Qualified and relevant experts:**
Invite experts who are interesting and relevant to participants and consider offering incentives to encourage their participation in the dialogue.
- **Motivation and incentives for participation:**
Emphasise the personal benefits for participants, such as gaining knowledge or developing social skills, and consider offering incentives to enhance motivation for participation.

3.3 Examples of good practices:

In the following are provided different examples of citizen dialogue formats and links to guidelines and further reading.

SNF web dialogues

The Stavros Niarchos Foundation (SNF) publishes dialogues. The Dialogues aspire to cultivate novel perspectives, establish connections for collaboration, and promote dynamic public discourse transcending geographical, social, and cultural boundaries. Through live debates, events, and diverse multimedia resources, SNF Dialogues facilitate the exchange of ideas, underscoring the importance of citizen expression and intercommunication, grounded in principles of fairness and inclusivity. Accessible to all, SNF Dialogues are free and welcoming to participants from all walks of life.

This is a nice example of moderated dialogues of a huge range of topics, with various experts and different stakeholders.

Appreciative Inquiry

Appreciative Inquiry (AI) is a structured approach employing inquiry and narrative-building techniques to stimulate innovation and creativity. AI empowers communities to recognize their strengths, formulate strategies, and ignite action toward substantial transformation.

Hence, AI can be considered a suitable method for conducting citizen dialogues of various scales.

Community dialogues

This example offers practical advice for facilitating a community dialogue in the realm of health. It outlines six scenarios, each emphasising existing communities and their potential interests in the subject matter. The format is flexible, understanding that community dialogues don't always require large groups of participants. These discussions can be intimate and held in easily accessible locations tailored to specific communities, such as schools, workplaces, churches, neighbourhoods, or government buildings. Additionally, the example provides a checklist for preparing such dialogues and a brief guide on hosting them.

Town hall debates

Town hall debates are suitable to engage with a larger group of people. This example is shared in the EC's Community of Practice of the Competence Centre on Participatory and Deliberative Democracy. It provides information about a citizen dialogue process reaching more than 200.000 citizens throughout five years. 1.767 town hall debates with national and local partners were held in 29 countries. They followed an open-door access policy. Open discussions were stimulated by moderators.

Science cafés

Science cafés are inclusive gatherings held in diverse casual venues, aiming to engage individuals who may not traditionally participate in scientific conversations. These events bring together various stakeholders and advocates, fostering an environment where everyone feels empowered to both listen to others and express their own ideas freely.

3.4 Citizen Dialogue formats implemented within FOODITY

3.4.1 Sofia

In Plovdiv, the cultural capital of Bulgaria, a Food Festival was held in the city park's alleys, where vendors from across Bulgaria were invited to host booths and promote their products. These included not only food and drink but also hand-made goods, pet food, and various entertainment sections. The event was held in celebration of the National Children's Holiday on June 1st, attracting many young families who enjoyed games, live music, and other activities throughout the weekend.

The Bulgarian hub team chose this event due to its focus on showcasing food from around the country, viewing it as the perfect opportunity to engage citizens from diverse age groups, backgrounds, and financial statuses. The goal was to hear their thoughts on how data can enhance

food choices and experiences, while also introducing them to the services developed within both the FOODITY project and its sister project, DRG4FOOD. A Bulgarian team, one of the winners of the DRG4FOOD Grant, accompanied the team to the event. The initiative aimed to raise awareness about GDPR, data rights, and EU Commission-funded projects, encouraging attendees to submit their own proposals for improving food-related solutions.

The hub team highlighted the FOOD 2030 program, explaining how data can drive the development of various products and services, ensuring transparency along the value chain and enhancing customer experience.

At the event, the team set up their own booth, featuring a FOODITY banner and distributing promotional flyers in both English and Bulgarian, as there were several expats present. The flyers provided an overview of the projects and the event's agenda.

The flyers also contained QR codes linking to an online survey, through which attendees shared their thoughts on the projects and services being developed. The survey included open-ended questions, inviting suggestions on how personal data could be used to improve individual experiences with food and nutrition.

3.4.2 Coimbra

The Portugal Hub Citizen Dialogue took place in Coimbra on 21 June 2024 from 12h00 – 14h00 CEST. The selected format for the event was a Lunch Talk, a discussion-driven event organised in a lunch setting, and supported on information and questions conveyed to participants. The event was organised alongside a lunch, following a less traditional approach, but with the objective of providing a different scenario for discussion aligned with one of the FOODITY pillars: food.

A presentation was used as support for the event, as it allowed the moderator to present relevant information about the project to facilitate discussion as well as the link to the Mentimeter app that was used for collecting feedback.

The discussion was fostered through several questions run on Mentimeter. Participants answered and results appeared in real-time. After each question, less common results were identified and participants were invited to verbalise

and explain their answers, and all participants were invited to comment.

At the end of the session, a short fun quiz was organised with food & nutrition related questions as a way to offer participants some FOODITY merchandising.

A total of 43 people participated in the event, mostly being associated with the target group of individuals with expected technological literacy.

3.4.3 Vienna

In October 2024, the hub team in Vienna organised a discussion at the Wissensraum in Vienna, focusing on the use of personal data in the nutrition sector. The event encouraged participants to reflect on how data collected through nutrition apps and loyalty cards is analysed and used in the digital age.

Two experts, one from the Association for Consumer Information and one from the Retail Association, provided insights on the topic. Together with the audience, they examined how data in the nutrition field is collected and utilised, addressing key topics such as company practices, consumer concerns, and ensuring responsible data handling. The open dialogue facilitated a constructive exchange between citizens and professionals, promoting a collaborative understanding of the role of data in modern food systems.

The event was complemented by a visual exhibition that presented outcomes from previous citizen workshops using the PhotoVoice method,

sparking further discussion.

Furthermore, the hub team organised an interactive workshop, engaging students aged 14 to 16 in a discussion on the role of nutrition and health data in the digital age. The workshop aimed to raise awareness among young people about how data from smartphones, wearables, and other technologies is collected, analysed, and often re-used by companies.

Through a series of interactive stations, students explored key questions such as how companies use their data, their concerns as consumers, and potential opportunities in data usage. The workshop encouraged students to reflect on these issues within the context of their daily lives, while considering the broader societal impacts of data usage.

Students also had the chance to view an exhibition showcasing the outcomes of three PhotoVoice workshops.

3.5 Experiences from dialogues

3.5.1 Sofia

At the **food festival**, the hub team informed attendees about the EU Commission's vision for sustainable food and nutrition, highlighting the projects they have funded and explaining how personal data is being used to provide valuable services while respecting GDPR rights. They distributed flyers to the crowd, allowing people to read further details at their own pace, fill in a survey via a QR code, and later share their thoughts and experiences. A follow-up discussion ensued, focusing on what the audience liked, their favourite projects, and what services they would be interested in seeing or using.

The team was surprised to discover that many attendees were unfamiliar with GDPR, which led to additional discussions introducing the concept and connecting it to familiar aspects such as cookies and opt-in processes. This sparked interest and enthusiasm among the crowd.

Conversations also revolved around shopping experiences and ideas for optimising home cooking. Many attendees were particularly impressed by the "Spotify for home cooking" concept, especially those with young children, as they were eager to involve their families in preparing healthy meals at home.

Another idea that resonated strongly was the cancer nutrition project, DIAITA. Some attendees shared personal experiences related to cancer patients, making them especially aware of the importance of such an initiative.

Overall, attendees were excited by these developments and were inspired to think about solutions they would like to see in the market. Some even expressed interest in applying for EU funding, asking the team about the process and their experiences. Several participants shared that they had already applied for funding or were planning to do so.

In conclusion, the discussions at the Food Fest were both productive and meaningful. The pleasant weather and the relaxed pace of the city encouraged attendees to stay and engage in extended conversations, which the team greatly appreciated.

3.5.2 Coimbra

To initiate the **lunch talk** event, participants were asked about their knowledge of GDPR, revealing that 76% were familiar with it, with only one participant lacking any knowledge. When asked about their concern with data sovereignty, 88% expressed varying levels of concern. Participants were also asked to describe what personal data meant to them, with terms like “private,” “confidential,” and “privacy” emerging prominently. Participants also mentioned various services and apps to which they share personal data, including retail stores and apps like Uber Eats, Strava, and Bolt.

The moderator facilitated a reflective discussion about the data generated through everyday activities, such as grocery shopping, and participants shared concerns about data exposure, phishing, identity theft, and misuse of personal data. Though most responses were negative, some participants recognized potential benefits, such as personalised services and consumption insights.

Participants then discussed barriers to data control, such as privacy, transparency, and interoperability challenges.

Later, the conversation shifted toward the use of personal data in improving food systems, with participants identifying seven key areas where data could be valuable: personalization, waste reduction, consumption patterns, healthy and sustainable eating, and enhancing food experiences. The event also featured a presentation on the six projects funded by the FOODITY open call, with particular interest in the STRADA project (detecting food spoilage) and the CSE-TKAS app (a “Kitchen Spotify” for families).

As the event concluded, participants reflected on their new knowledge and concerns, with many expressing heightened awareness about their personal data. Some expressed interest in participating in future project calls, while others emphasised the importance of increased control over

personal data. The session also highlighted the participants’ growing awareness of the relationship between data control and personal freedom.

The session used interactive tools like Mentimeter to engage participants, allowing for anonymous input and more honest responses. However, some logistical challenges were noted, including the difficulty in attracting participants and the impact of a self-service lunch format, which momentarily affected participant engagement. Overall, the session was considered a success, with valuable insights gained regarding personal data management and its broader implications.

3.5.3 Vienna

The discussion event covered various aspects of data collection in the nutrition and retail sectors, highlighting the practices of companies like pharmaceutical firms and retailers that collect consumer data to understand customer behaviour and deliver personalised advertising. Although the GDPR exists, it is not widely followed, and many consumers are unaware of their rights, such as revoking consent for data collection, especially in the case of loyalty cards.

Data has immense value for companies, enabling them to save money and optimise their advertising, yet consumers benefit less from it. For example, they might compare prices less frequently because they receive discounts. However, data could be used positively, such as in efforts to reduce food waste.

Loyalty programs have become crucial for retailers due to high competition, and customers can choose whether to allow profiling. Retailers track details like when, where, and at what price customers make purchases. Although retailers in

Austria, like Lidl and Spar, do not share data with each other, this practice is more common in other countries.

Specific examples were discussed, such as the “Jö-card”, where companies collect extensive data about consumers, from car ownership to shopping habits. While companies invest in data protection to comply with regulations, concerns about privacy persist, especially regarding apps like “Temu”, which reportedly collects and sells user data.

In the end, although consumers are more informed today and compare prices, loyalty to retailers has decreased, and data privacy remains a neglected issue for many who feel they have “nothing to hide.”

Another issue raised was the ability to legally purchase addresses in Austria and how comparison platforms gather massive amounts of data. Free apps often generate revenue through data sales. Retailers may save around €100 per data set annually by targeting ads more effectively.

The conversation also touched on the risks for

consumers, such as being overly influenced by targeted ads or facing discrimination, like higher insurance premiums based on personal data. Privacy concerns were emphasised, especially with data potentially being shared with insurance companies or other third parties. The event concluded with advice on protecting privacy, including clearing cookies and understanding consent settings, while highlighting the dangers of apps, especially those targeted at minors, which may lead to debt accumulation.

In the **school workshop** the hub team also discussed why data holds such high value for companies. The students learned that the more detailed the information about individuals, the more accurately businesses can tailor products and services to specific needs and preferences. This allows companies to target their marketing more effectively, predict consumer behaviour, and increase sales. We highlighted how data enables firms to gain insights into customers’ habits, preferences, and even potential future actions, making it a crucial asset in the digital economy.

Awareness raising campaign

This section describes the strategy and actions that are part of the **FOODITY citizen awareness raising campaign**, led by AUS in collaboration with SPL, F6S, and ZSI.

This awareness raising campaign is the manifestation of the overarching mission of the project to inform and inspire citizens about the importance of data in the food and nutrition arena. It also addresses the relevant role of data in creating healthier and more sustainable food systems, supporting informed choices by users, and building a community based on a set of values.

The **campaign's primary goal is to deepen citizens' understanding** of how food and nutrition data influence personal health, community well-being, and broader environmental goals. Through accessible, visually engaging, and interactive content, the campaign provides essential knowledge to **help citizens make informed choices**.

By presenting content that connects with citizens' values, FOODITY intends to build a campaign that **empowers citizens**, by making them feel involved in the shaping of the future of food data.

The campaign is also designed to **attract new audiences**, increase engagement on the project channels, and establish a growing community, hence amplifying the reach of FOODITY's message through broad, consistent, and multichannel dissemination.

4.1 Methodological approach

Regarding the **methodological approach followed to create this campaign**, it builds on previous engagement activities with the community, as well as on the research insights obtained through the project, to create a strategy that resonates with a diverse audience.

The **building blocks of the campaign** are:

Community insights: several sources coming from the community itself are taken into account to build a campaign that can truly connect with a wide range of citizens, such as the results of the participatory PhotoVoice Workshops, which offer citizens a way to voice their perspectives. Participants can share their concerns, through guided activities, including photography and storytelling, which highlights their views on the role of data in food systems.

Citizen dialogues and stakeholder engagement: insights from PhotoVoice workshops are used to inform structured citizen dialogues, where participants discuss food and nutrition data's societal impact. These dialogues can serve as a platform for discussions. Surveys are also distributed to participants during industry related events to gather more information, and the advances of the pilots coming from the open calls are also taken into account.

In the framework of this Strategy, other **internal inputs** are analysed, like the research produced by the project, containing literature review and interviews, and other sources of information such as brainstorming sessions held by the consortium (see Figure 4) to refine the key messages to be delivered to the target audiences.

Awareness Raising Campaign

Drawing from the workshops and dialogues insights, and other inputs coming from multiple sources, an analysis was performed by AUS, with the support of SPL, F6S, and ZSI, which culminated in the design of a multi-channel strategy to ensure that the awareness raising campaign's **messages reaches a broad, diverse audience.**

This approach uses **various digital and in-person channels to deliver key messages**, reinforcing FOODITY's commitment to accessible, inclusive, and engaging communication.

The methodology is built to **adapt to evolving audience needs and to track and measure campaign impact** continuously. Feedback loops within the campaign enable ongoing refinement based on real-time metrics and audience reactions, ensuring relevance and resonance.

4.2 Campaign content and key messages

The FOODITY citizen awareness raising campaign is structured to provide relatable, clear, and actionable messages that empower citizens to understand and engage with food and nutrition data responsibly. Key messages are crafted to address specific concerns and promote critical thinking about the role of data in personal and environmental well-being.

The campaign highlights the importance of **understanding what personal data citizens generate, how it is shared, and its implications for food systems**. By explaining what data practices involve, the campaign encourages citizens to make data-conscious choices, contributing to a transparent ecosystem.

FOODITY also seeks to **empower individuals** with knowledge about data sovereignty and ethical data-sharing practices. Messages are curated

to emphasise **citizens' rights to control their personal data and make informed decisions** regarding their food and nutrition choices.

The campaign tries to make citizens aware of the **link between responsible data sharing behaviours and sustainability**, highlighting that each individual's actions, when based on a sustainable mindset, contribute to healthier food systems and have a positive environmental impact.

By sharing **success stories, best practices, and positive examples of food data use**, the campaign intends to promote collaboration and inspire a shared responsibility to protect data rights and advance sustainable food choices.

4.3 Personas and target groups

Understanding the ideal “personas” and “target groups” is an essential step for creating an effective citizen awareness campaign. The subjects can have very different responses to a message depending on their set of values or individual characteristics. By taking this into account when designing a campaign, even if it is addressed to a broad audience, it will be possible to create messages that resonate with the different subsets of the targeted audience, increasing its impact and making a better use of the resources available.

By defining the characteristics of the different “personas”, it will be possible to establish the preferred communication channel to be used for each one, or create messages tailored to their specific needs, while at the same time making sure that they are inclusive.

Hence, a campaign based on well-defined groups can create better connections with its audience and encourage interaction.

To tailor messages effectively, the FOODITY citizen awareness campaign defines **three primary personas**, each representing a distinct audience segment:

Figure 4 Persona 1

Alex

Young individual (student)

Age: 18-25

- Income: Less disposable income.
- Education: High school to college-educated.
- Location: Suburban/urban areas and university cities/towns.
- Interests: Sustainable living and healthy eating trends, environmental and social causes, sport and fitness.
- Behaviour: Follows and engages with popular sustainability, fitness and health influencers and vloggers on Instagram, TikTok and YouTube; participates in online/local sport classes and university-led/entertainment and sustainability initiatives, seeks easy and actionable tips on sustainable living and healthy eating.

Figure 5 Persona 2

Blake

Young adult

Age: 25-40

- Income: Middle to high.
- Education: College-educated.
- Location: Suburban and urban areas.
- Interests: Healthy eating, wellness habits, sustainable living and environmental conservation, prefers eco-friendly food options.
- Behaviour: shops for eco-friendly food options, follows nutrition, fitness and health experts on social media (Instagram, Tik Tok and YouTube) and uses X and WhatsApp groups to stay informed, and listens to podcasts in this field, participates in local/online (webinars) fitness classes and eco-friendly and wellness-oriented events, seeks advice on healthy habits and balanced nutrition (i.e. through experts on long-form articles and stories (in the media or online platforms) and videos, or in apps).

Figure 6 Persona 3

Charlie

Health and environmentally- conscious consumer

Age: 40-65

- Income: Middle to high.
- Education: College-educated - or with intellectual pursuits
- Location: Suburban/urban areas.
- Interests: Healthy lifestyle, sustainability and eco-friendly practices, health, wellness and parenting influencers, eco-friendly food options.
- Behaviour: Frequently uses health and fitness apps, engages with content related to nutrition, fitness, and wellness on social media (YouTube), uses X and LinkedIn and is subscribed to different newsletters to stay informed and consume long-form content, participates in family-oriented environmental activities, local and online events, seeks information on balanced diets and sustainable eating habits.

By addressing the unique concerns and values of each persona, the FOODITY campaign ensures that its message is targeted, engaging, and relevant to diverse citizen groups.

4.4 Examples of activities to be implemented

This section outlines a set of examples of activities to be implemented as part of the citizen awareness campaign and describes, among other aspects, their relationship with the communication channels to be used, to ensure continuous engagement and alignment with the project's goals.

Social media campaigns can be launched using the Key Messages developed during brainstorming sessions. These messages, as prioritised by the participating parts, can be disseminated through social media channels. These social media campaigns aim to raise awareness by presenting impactful content tailored to each platform. aid campaigns can also be part of this effort.

Here are presented examples of the social media posts used as part of a paid campaign.

Figure 7 Key Messages Campaign - Social Media Posts

Online Surveys can be created to assess citizens' awareness of their data rights, especially when using food and nutrition apps or services. Through a short survey, participants can gain insights into how their personal data is used and how it directly impacts their daily choices.

Distributed at sector-specific events or in other relevant contexts, the survey allows attendees to self-evaluate their understanding and provides valuable feedback. These surveys can also be used in other channels, such as social media or websites.. Insights gathered from surveys can help shape future campaigns, ensuring that the content is adapted to address common gaps in understanding, and highlight areas of interest

Figure 8 Online Survey

Awareness Raising Campaign

The **citizen awareness raising campaigns should evolve with the implementation of the project.** Hence, new actions can be designed and adapted to the inputs obtained from the results of other actions, such as surveys or engagement metrics from social media campaigns, helping emphasise the most misunderstood topics or those generating the highest levels of interest. Further examples of activities part of a citizen awareness raising campaign can include:

- **Interactive campaigns** designed to provide deeper insights into areas where citizens demonstrate low knowledge, fostering both education and engagement. These can be **short-term topic specific campaigns.**
- **Recipe book** integrating data facts with recipes contributed by relevant stakeholders, such as experts and innovators. Each recipe can feature a relevant data fact, providing a creative way to insert food-related data.
- **Marketing materials** aligned with the cam-

paign's focus to enhance engagement further.

- **Additional formats should always be explored,** to increase variety and appeal across audience segments, and content adapted for each persona, ensuring relevance and impact.

Based on all previous sources of information and on the designed strategy, a wide range of content can be produced and **distributed through various channels:**

- **Visual and Video Content:** Infographics, short videos, and visually engaging posts to simplify complex data and make it appealing to diverse audiences.
- **Social Media, Newsletters, Website:** Leveraging the size of the following and community, to provide in-depth perspectives on food data issues, share best practices, and encourage sustainable choices.
- **Storytelling:** Personal stories and interviews

with members of the community, innovators, and experts can be shared to build authenticity.

- **In-Person and Virtual Events:** To complement digital efforts, participation in events, interacting with the public and experts, can provide opportunities for dialogue and knowledge exchange.

Figure 9 Main characteristics of the contents produced

By combining these activities and leveraging insights from implemented actions, the campaign remains dynamic and current, aiming to maximise its impact.

Lastly, attention should be paid to the **monitoring of the campaign results** (e.g., social media impressions, website visits, video views, newsletter engagement), **as well as the collection of feedback**. This data informs on adjustments to messaging, content focus, and distribution methods to enhance engagement and maximise reach.

This approach was designed to ensure that the FOODITY campaign reaches a diverse audience, building a knowledgeable community that values transparency, responsible food data use, and sustainable food choices.

Conclusions

5.1 PhotoVoice workshops

The PhotoVoice workshops have yielded valuable insights and outcomes, reflecting both our participants' engagement and the efficacy of the method. Initially, it was aimed to recruit between 15 to 20 participants per workshop. However, it was found that working with smaller groups of 8 to 10 participants proved to be particularly beneficial. Smaller group sizes fostered a more intimate and focused environment, enhancing both discussion and creativity. Larger groups would have demanded significantly more resources, potentially compromising the quality of interaction and output.

One effective measure implemented was offering financial compensation to participants. This decision underscored the value of their time and contributions, leading to consistent participation and heightened commitment throughout the workshops. This approach not only reinforced a sense of appreciation but also encouraged more profound engagement from each individual.

While the PhotoVoice method is traditionally associated with community development projects, the experience of the team demonstrates that it is equally suitable for more complex and abstract topics. The method's adaptable nature allowed participants to explore intricate questions and themes, showcasing their unique perspectives through photography and discussion. However, it was learned that a crucial component of success in these scenarios is providing sufficient time for participants to understand and internalise the workshop's focus. Without this preparation, participants might struggle to align their creative outputs with the intended theme.

To maximise effectiveness, it is recommended a clear, structured approach that includes an initial phase where participants can immerse themselves in the topic. This phase should be designed to facilitate comprehension and comfort with the workshop's objectives, ensuring that participants can produce meaningful and thoughtful work. Additionally, offering guidance and support throughout the process proved essential, as it helped participants navigate the complexity of abstract questions and contributed to higher-quality results.

5.2 Citizen Dialogues

Reflecting on the three citizen dialogue events, several key lessons emerge that can guide future initiatives.

Firstly, the method of engagement profoundly affects participant involvement. The use of interactive tools like Mentimeter allowed for anonymous and honest feedback. Creating a casual and interactive environment facilitated open conversations, making participants more comfortable in sharing their thoughts.

Similar to the PhotoVoice workshops the “10 Lev for 10 Minutes” campaign in Sofia was successful, demonstrating that innovative and relatable incentives can significantly boost participation.

Like many other examples, the citizen dialogue process proved that effective recruitment and communication strategies are essential. Collaboration with local partners like Wissens°raum in Vienna or Festival organisers in Sofia revealed that

aligning outreach strategies is vital.

In essence, these events showcased that successful engagement is a balance of innovative techniques, strategic planning, and efficient logistics. Future events should integrate interactive tools that encourage honest participation, offer creative incentives aligned with participant interests, and ensure logistical arrangements that keep the focus on meaningful dialogue. Refining outreach strategies and improving communication with potential attendees can enhance recruitment and participation rates.

5.4 Campaigning

The FOODITY citizen awareness raising campaign is designed to help people better understand the role of data in food and nutrition, encouraging citizens to make informed decisions by highlighting issues like data rights, ethical data-sharing, and the link between individual actions and sustainable food systems. By sharing relatable stories and clear messages, the campaign's intent is building awareness and inspiring people to take action.

The campaign strategy draws from real experiences and research, including workshops, citizen dialogues, and other inputs from the FOODITY community. By defining different personas, the team has created messages that speak to the values and interests of specific audience groups. This approach helps make the campaign more relatable and engaging for a wide range of people. Using multiple platforms like social media, surveys, and in-person events is helping the campaign reach a broad audience.

On a campaign of this nature, the focus should remain on raising awareness, empowering citizens, and fostering a sense of community, with the activities evolving based on feedback and insights gathered throughout the project.

Citizen Empowerment Handbook

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Handbook Citizen Empowerment

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